

Deterioration of CFRP and GFRP in Salt Water

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ABSTRACT

Specimens of carbon fiber or glass fiber unidirectionally reinforced epoxy resin (CFRP and GFRP) were boiled for periods from 2 to 100 hours in salt waters (0-23 % of NaCl) or immersed in salt waters at 30°C or 20°C under atmospheric or higher pressure. Fatigue tests were also carried out in salt waters at 30°C. The water absorptions of CFRP and GFRP boiled decreased with increasing concentration of salt. Even at 4 vol % of void, they were smaller in a 9 % salt water than that in water. In salt waters under a pressure of 78.5 MPa, the water absorptions of CFRP and GFRP specimens also decreased with increasing concentration of salt. In all of the immersions, their flexural strength and inter-laminar shear strength (ILSS) decreased with increasing water absorption. These results showed that salt water was less harmful to CFRP and GFRP than water.

INTRODUCTION

In the marine field, GFRP is a material which is taking the place of metal from the body of small ships owing to its properties of non-corrosion (1). And now, CFRP begins to be used in parts of ships (2). Hereafter, CFRP will expand uses also in the marine field because of its high specific strength and high specific modulus, though high cost.

The conditions under which CFRP or GFRP expand uses in the marine aspects are their good durability and small dilatation in size. Accordingly, it is necessary to grasp the life prediction and reliability of CFRP and GFRP in sea water exactly. Further, to improve the durability the reason of deterioration is necessary to be cleared up. However, the deterioration of CFRP and GFRP in sea water is not sufficiently examined.

In this paper, from these points of view, CFRP and GFRP were immersed in salt waters under the different conditions of immersion, and their dependences in mechanical properties and size on immersion time, amount of water absorbed and concentration of salt were examined.

EXPERIMENTAL

Carbon fiber TORAYCA T300 (Toray Ind., Inc.) and glass roving RS 120E-601DB (Nitto Boseki Co., Ltd.) were used as reinforcements, and epoxy resin EPIKOTE 828 cured with BF₃-MEA was used as a matrix.

Each of the fibers was wound on a metal frame and was immersed in an acetone solution of the uncured resin. Then, the fiber impregnated with resin was heated to pre-cure at 90°C for 2 hours. Prepreg sheets obtained were demounted from the frame. Several sheets of the prepreg were stacked, cured at 170°C under pressure for one hour and aftercured at 200°C for one hour without pressure. Plates of unidirectionally reinforced CFRP and GFRP were obtained.

From them, specimens of 120 mm long, 10 mm wide and 2 mm thick and 20 mm long, 10 mm wide and 2 mm thick were prepared to test flexural strength and ILSS, respectively. For tensile strength test and fatigue test, specimens of 120 mm long and 10 mm wide were prepared. And, according to RAE method (3), a waist of 125 mm radius was shaped on each of them by reducing the thickness at the center to 1 mm.

Immersion in boiling salt waters was carried out for 2, 10 or 100 hours in a 2 liters round-bottomed flask equiped with a mantle-heater. For immersion in pressed water, an apparatus of autoclave type was used. The diameter of its cylinder was 50 mm and the inside volume was 600 ml. Specimens were immersed in salt waters under various pressures in the range from 4.9 MPa to 98 MPa for one month or under a pressure of 78.5 MPa for various periods in the range from 1 to 12 months at 20°C. Tension-tension fatigue tests in salt waters were carried out at 30°C at a frequency of 4 Hz. A water bath for the fatigue test in salt waters was made of Teflon bellows, and it was set up in a fatigue test machine.

Density was measured by using a pycnometer and distilled water at 25°C. Fiber weight content, W_f (%), was measured by a method of eliminating the resin in an oxidizing flame of a Bunsen burner for CFRP and in a crucible furnace at 650°C in an air for GFRP. Fiber volume content, V_f (%), and void volume content, V_v (%), were calculated from densities of composites, d_c , and matrix resin, d_m , and W_f .

After immersion, water absorption, Q (mg/cm³), was calculated by equation (1).

$$Q = \frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_1} \times d_c \times \frac{100}{100 - V_f} \times 1000 \quad (1)$$

where W_1 and W_2 are the weights of the specimen before and after immersion. Q is a value per unit volume of the region except fiber in CFRP or GFRP.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Effects of Absorbed Water on the Strength

Flexural strengths and ILSSs of CFRP and GFRP immersed in boiling water and salt waters are shown in Figures 1(a) and (b). They decrease with increasing amount of absorbed water. Flexural strength and ILSS before immersion were 1.45 GPa and 78.7 MPa for CFRP, respectively, and 1.23 GPa and 79.8 MPa for GFRP, respectively. The above mentioned results coincide with those obtained by Judd (3) on ILSS.

When a FRP specimen in which water is absorbed is bent or drawn for test, internal pressure is considered to be generated in the water residing in the interface of fiber and resin or in the voids according to the deformation of specimen, and this internal pressure is considered to cause cracks in the interface of fiber and resin or/and on the wall of void. The larger the amount of water absorbed is, the higher the internal pressure becomes.

Figure 1

Effect of water absorption on flexural strength (a) and ILSS (b) retention of CFRP and GFRP immersed in boiling water

Concentration of salt (%) ———
 ●, ○ - 0 ; ▲, △ - 4 ; ■, □ - 9 ; ▼, ▽ - 23

Figure 2

Effect of water absorption on dilatation strain in width of CFRP and GFRP immersed in boiling water

Figure 3

Effect of concentration of salt on water absorption of CFRP (a) and GFRP (b) immersed in boiling water

Figure 4

Effect of void content on water absorption of CFRP (a) and GFRP (b) immersed in boiling water for 100 hours

Lengths of CFRP and GFRP were unchanged, but their widths increased with increasing water absorption. But they were independent of concentration of salt, as shown in Figure 2. Dilatation (%) in width is provided theoretically by equation (2).

$$\text{Dilatation} = \frac{b_1 - b_2}{b_1} \times 100 = \frac{100 - V_f}{2000} \times Q \quad (2)$$

where b_1 and b_2 are the widths of the specimen before and after immersion. But the observed values in Figure 2 are smaller than those from the theory. On the dilatation curve of CFRP observed, there is a change in slope at a water absorption of 20 mg/cm^3 . The discrepancy between the theory and the observed data is considered to be partially owing to voids in the samples. On the other hand, decrease in mechanical properties of CFRP and GFRP immersed in boiling water were not affected directly by void content.

Factors Effecting on Water Absorption

Figures 3(a) and (b) show the results of investigation on the effect of concentration of salt on the water absorption. The amounts of water absorbed in both CFRP and GFRP increase with increasing immersion time from 2 to 100 hours, and at the same immersion time they decrease with increasing concentration of salt.

Figures 4(a) and (b) show the influence of void content on the water absorption. The amounts of water absorbed of CFRP and GFRP increase with increasing void content. This result suggests that the content of water absorbed is different between the regions of resin and void and the distribution of water absorbed is larger in void than that in resin. If a void content of 4 % is filled with water, the amount of water is about 80 mg/cm^3 at $V_f = 50 \%$ and about 100 mg/cm^3 at $V_f = 60 \%$. In the case of GFRP immersed in water in Figure 4(b), though the V_f is over 50 %, an increase in water absorption by increasing void content from 0 % to 4 % must be about 60 mg/cm^3 , and this value is smaller than the calculated value showed above. It is considered for this reason that the absorption has not reached to the equilibrium state. The difference between the amounts of water absorbed in water and in a 9 % salt water is relatively smaller near a void content of 0 %. But at higher void contents the amounts of water absorbed in a 9 % salt water are smaller than those in water.

When specimens of CFRP and GFRP the outer surfaces of which were coated with a kind of water repellent were immersed in boiling water, the water absorption decreased and ILSS retention became higher.

Immersion in Salt Waters under Various Pressures

Figures 5(a) and (b) show the effect of concentration of salt on water absorption when samples were immersed in salt water under various pressures for one month. The water absorption under an atmospheric pressure at 30°C decrease with increasing concentration of salt. In Figures 5(a) and (b) it is shown that under higher pressures the water absorptions tend to increase with concentration of salt, though the water absorption at 4 % is smaller than those at 9 %. The drops in amount of water absorbed at 4 % are experimental errors probably.

Water absorption of specimens immersed in water and a 9 % salt water under a pressure of 78.5 MPa are shown against immersion periods in Figure 6. The water absorptions of CFRP and GFRP increase with increasing period and they are less in 9 % salt water than those in water. The void contents of specimens in Figure 5 and 6 were 0.9-1.3 % for CFRP and 0.1 % for GFRP. For the specimens of CFRP and GFRP shown in Figure 6 flexural strengths and ILSSs decreased with increasing water absorption, regardless of concentration of salt.

For the CFRP and GFRP specimens immersed in boiling salt water, an atmospheric pressure water and a 78.5 MPa pressed water, flexural strengths and ILSSs were plotted against the amounts of water absorbed. In the all cases they decreased linearly with increasing amount of water absorbed, and the degree to

Figure 5

Effect of concentration of salt on water absorption of CFRP (a) and GFRP (b) immersed under various pressures for one month

Figure 6

Water absorption as a function of period for CFRP and GFRP immersed under a pressure of 78.5 MPa

Figure 7

Effect of concentration of salt on fatigue strength of CFRP and GFRP at 10^4 and 10^7 cycles

which the flexural strengths and ILSSs decreased was the largest for the case in boiling salt water and the next for the case in a 78.5 MPa pressed water. This result shows that the high temperature and high pressure give more remarkable influence on the deterioration of CFRP and GFRP than water absorption, though the water absorption has a remarkable influence on the deterioration of them.

It can be explained from lowering in the chemical potential of water that the water absorption decreases with increasing concentrations of salt, as shown in Figures from 3 to 6.

Tension-tension Fatigue Tests in Salt Waters

Fatigue data of CFRP and GFRP are very important for the design of structures, but they are scarcely obtained in water. Then, tension-tension fatigue tests were carried out in salt waters, and S-N lines were obtained in a range from 10^4 to 10^7 cycles.

Tensile strengths and ILSSs of specimens used in the fatigue tests were 1.63 GPa and 84.0 MPa for CFRP, respectively, and 1.15 GPa and 77.6 MPa for GFRP, respectively. Void volume contents of CFRP and GFRP were 1.0 and 0%. As Aluminum tabs which were bonded to the part of grips of fatigue specimens corroded in salt water, they were coated with water repellent, though such treatment was not completely enough to prevent corrosion.

Plots of the fatigue data obtained could be approximated to straight lines. S-N lines of CFRP shifted to a lower side of stress as concentration of salt increased. In the case of GFRP, the lines at concentration of 0% and 4% overlapped each other. But the line at a concentration of 9% was located at a higher stress.

Fatigue strengths at 10^4 and 10^7 cycles were estimated from the straight lines obtained from fatigue data by using the least squares method, and they were plotted in Figure 7 as a function of concentration of salt. The fatigue

strengths of GFRP increase with increasing concentration of salt. But those of CFRP decrease with increasing concentration of salt. In these fatigue tests, the water absorptions in CFRP and GFRP are also considered to decrease with increasing concentration of salt, in a similar manner as seen in boiling water, in an atmospheric pressure water and in a 78.5 MPa pressed water. Accordingly, the above mentioned results of GFRP can be explained from the water absorption. On the other hand, the fatigue data of CFRP are results opposite to them, but these results are not considered to suggest that salt water accelerates the deterioration of CFRP. A few reasons why such results of CFRP occurred are considered as below. The CFRP specimens were necessary to grip with greater force than those of GFRP, because CFRP specimens were tested under higher loads and in addition the tabs were corroded with salt waters. Then the rupture might occur between tabs in the CFRP specimens. The bending stress might also occur in the CFRP specimens owing to the heterogeneous corrosion of tabs. And these might lower the fatigue strength of CFRP.

Fatigue strengths of CFRP and GFRP at 10^7 cycles in salt waters were considerably lower than those in air. This suggests the effect of water on fatigue behavior.

CONCLUSIONS

CFRP and GFRP were immersed in salt waters and following results were obtained. 1) The amount of water absorbed in CFRP and GFRP decreased with increasing concentration of salt, and 2) their flexural strength and ILSS decreased and their width increased with increasing amount of water absorbed. These results show that the salt water does not accelerate the deterioration of CFRP and GFRP.

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